

EFFECTS OF SALINITY AND INDOLE-3-ACETIC ACID ON GROWTH AND PHYCOCYANIN BIOSYNTHESIS IN *Arthrospira platensis*

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SUMMARY

Arthrospira platensis is a rich source of minerals, essential amino acids, and antioxidant pigments such as chlorophyll and phycocyanin. Phycocyanin is a high-value antioxidant pigment, yet cultivation strategies to improve its accumulation without compromising biomass remain limited. This study evaluated the synergistic effects of sodium chloride (NaCl, 100 - 300 mM) and exogenous indole-3-acetic acid (IAA, 1 mg/L) on growth and phycocyanin biosynthesis in *A. platensis*. Initial screening showed that 100 mM of NaCl produced the highest biomass (8.97 ± 2.80 g/L) but reduced phycocyanin content (6.39 ± 1.03 mg/g). To improve the pigment yield, two cultivation strategies were investigated: co-supplementation with IAA on day 0 (single-stage) and day 5 (two-stage). Compared with the controls, single-stage co-supplementation produced the highest biomass (7.25 ± 0.27 g/L) and phycocyanin content (13.07 ± 0.85 mg/g), while the two-stage approach also maintained stable biomass (6.00 ± 0.14 g/L) and enhanced phycocyanin accumulation (12.05 ± 0.43 mg/g). These results demonstrated that moderate salinity combined with IAA enhanced phycocyanin productivity while maintaining growth, providing a practical strategy for pigment-enriched *A. platensis* cultivation.

Keywords: *Arthrospira platensis*, indole-3-acetic acid, phycocyanin, salinity stress, two-stage cultivation.

INTRODUCTION

Arthrospira platensis (also known as *Spirulina platensis*), is a photosynthetic, filamentous, helical-shaped cyanobacterium that thrives in alkaline waters under high temperatures and intense sunlight (Akbarnezhad *et al.*, 2020; Wan *et al.*, 2016). *A. platensis* contains up to 70% protein (dry weight) and is a rich source of essential fatty acids, amino acids, minerals, vitamins, and antioxidant pigments such as chlorophyll a (Chl-a), carotenoids (Car), phycocyanin (PC), and polysaccharides. These compounds are associated with a wide range of health benefits and potential applications in managing non-communicable diseases, including diabetes mellitus, hyperlipidemia, oxidative stress-related disorders, inflammation, allergies, hypertension, and certain cancer (Lafarga *et al.*, 2020). The growth and pigment biosynthesis of *A. platensis* are strongly influenced by several environmental and nutritional factors such as light intensity, pH, salinity, temperature, and nutrient composition. Among these, sodium chloride (NaCl) stress affects osmotic balance and cellular metabolism, often leading to changes in pigment composition. Likewise, phytohormones such as indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) have been reported to stimulate growth and secondary metabolite production (Jasuja, 2014). While the individual effects of NaCl and IAA on pigment biosynthesis have been studied, their synergistic interactions, particularly in regulating phycocyanin biosynthesis, remain poorly understood. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the effects of NaCl, IAA, and their combinations on the growth and phycocyanin biosynthesis in *A. platensis*. The findings are expected to inform the development of efficient, cost-effective microalgal cultivation strategies for the sustainable production of high-value pigments and nutraceutical compounds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: *A. platensis* was obtained from the Research Institute for Aquaculture II (Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam) and stored at 4°C. Prior to each experiment, seed cultures were inoculated for 10 - 14 days in 500 mL of Zarrouk medium (Zarrouk, 1966) until reaching an optical density at 680 nm (OD_{680}) of approximately 1.0. The seed culture was inoculated into experimental treatments at a ratio of 1% (v/v). All containers were maintained at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under continuous white fluorescent illumination (3000 - 4000 lux) and aerated continuously (2.7 L/min) using air pumps equipped with 0.22- μm PTFE filters.

The composition of Zarrouk medium was (g/L): NaHCO_3 , 16.8; NaCl, 1.0; NaNO_3 , 2.5; K_2HPO_4 , 0.5; K_2SO_4 , 1.0; EDTA, 0.08; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.2; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01; $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.04; and micronutrient A5, 1 mL/L. The micronutrient solution A5 contained (mg/100 mL): H_3BO_3 , 286; $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 250; $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 22.2; $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 7.9; and $\text{NaMoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.1).

Experimental setup

Preliminary evaluation of the effects of NaCl and IAA

The experiment consisted of four treatments: (1) Zarrouk medium (control); (2) Zarrouk medium supplemented

with NaCl (100 mM); (3) Zarrouk medium supplemented with indole-3-acetic acid (IAA, 1 mg/L); and (4) Zarrouk medium supplemented with both NaCl and IAA.

Salinity (NaCl) dose-response

To examine salinity effects, the experiment was performed with four treatments: (1) Zarrouk medium (control); (2) Zarrouk medium supplemented with 100 mM NaCl (4.85 g/L); (3) Zarrouk medium supplemented with 200 mM NaCl (10.70 g/L); and (4) Zarrouk medium supplemented with 300 mM NaCl (16.55 g/L). In this trial, NaCl stress was induced either at day 0 (single-stage cultivation) or at day 5 (two-stage cultivation) after an initial biomass accumulation phase.

Synergistic effects of NaCl and IAA

In this trial, IAA (1 mg/L) was supplemented in combination with NaCl (0 - 300 mM). Both NaCl and IAA were added to the cultures either at day 0 or day 5 of the cultivation.

Cultivation conditions and sampling

All experiments were performed in triplicates in 1000-mL glass containers. Cultures were continuously aerated and maintained at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under continuous white fluorescent light (3000 - 4000 lux). Biomass was harvested on days 5 and 10 by filtration through a 50- μm pore-size cloth. Fresh biomass was determined gravimetrically. Phycocyanin was extracted using an ultrasound-assisted method with 1.5% CaCl_2 solution, following the procedure described by Ilter *et al.* (2018).

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's HSD post hoc tests were performed using GraphPad Prism 10.5 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA). Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$. Phycocyanin contents were expressed on a fresh-weight basis (mg/g fw).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of co-supplementation of NaCl and IAA

Figure 1. Effects of NaCl-induced stress and IAA supplementation on fresh biomass (A) and phycocyanin yield; (B) of *A. platensis* over 10 days of cultivation.

Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; and ***: $p < 0.001$.

The combination of NaCl and IAA significantly enhanced both biomass and phycocyanin yield in *A. platensis* compared with NaCl alone or the control (Figure 1). The treatment with 100 mM of NaCl + 1 mg/L IAA produced the highest fresh biomass, reaching 5.33 ± 0.12 g/L on day 5 and 10.32 ± 0.25 g/L on day 10, approximately 1.5-fold higher than the control (4.30 ± 0.17 g/L and 7.42 ± 0.22 g/L, respectively). In addition, the phycocyanin content also increased significantly, reaching 10.25 ± 0.29 mg/g on day 5 and 13.26 ± 0.91 mg/g on day 10, compared with 8.45 ± 0.21 mg/g and 9.35 ± 0.27 mg/g in the control ($p < 0.001$). This synergistic effect suggests that IAA may mitigate salt-induced stress by enhancing osmotic regulation and stimulating secondary metabolite pathways. IAA has been associated with the activation of antioxidant systems and nitrogen assimilation in cyanobacteria, which are critical for phycobiliprotein biosynthesis (Tiwari *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, Silveira *et al.* (2023) reported that IAA supplementation enhanced biomass accumulation by 31.2% relative to the control. The consistency between the present study and previous research further highlights the potential of IAA in enhancing salt stress tolerance and improving pigment productivity in *A. platensis*.

Effects of different NaCl concentrations

NaCl supplementation exerted a dose-dependent influence on both biomass production and phycocyanin biosynthesis (Figure 2). After 10 days, cultures supplemented with 100 mM of NaCl achieved the highest fresh biomass (8.97 ± 2.80 g/L), significantly higher than the control and other treatments ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, biomass decreased to 7.26 ± 1.87 g/L at 200 mM of NaCl and was strongly inhibited at 300 mM of NaCl (4.59 ± 0.35 g/L). Phycocyanin contents were comparable across treatments during the first five days ($p > 0.05$); however, from day 5 to day 10, all NaCl-treated cultures showed significant reductions, with the lowest phycocyanin content recorded at 300 mM of NaCl treatment (4.68 ± 0.58 mg/g) compared to the control (10.35 ± 0.64 mg/g; $p < 0.01$). These results suggested that while 100 mM of NaCl might transiently promote biomass production, prolonged exposure or elevated salinity suppressed pigment biosynthesis, likely due to osmotic stress, ion toxicity, and impaired nitrogen assimilation affecting the phycobiliprotein biosynthetic pathway. To mitigate the inhibitory effects while retaining the stimulatory benefits, a two-stage cultivation strategy was employed by supplementing 100 mM of NaCl on day 5 after an initial biomass accumulation phase. This approach maintained biomass yield (8.15 ± 0.37 g/L) comparable to the single-stage cultivation, and simultaneously increased phycocyanin content to 10.46 ± 1.63 mg/g, which was approximately double that of the single-stage 100 mM NaCl treatment (6.39 ± 1.03 mg/g). These findings were consistent with Yu *et al.* (2024), who reported that 100 mM of NaCl optimized biomass yield compared to higher salt levels, and that supplementation with exogenous glycine-betaine further enhanced biomass and phycocyanin accumulation under salt stress (Yu *et al.*, 2024). Yu *et al.* (2023) demonstrated that two-stage cultivation with NaCl and glucose increased phycocyanin productivity up to 115.56 mg/L, suggesting the effectiveness of phase-targeted stress induction for maintaining biomass and pigment yields. Overall, these results highlighted the potential of the two-phase cultivation as a practical strategy to balance biomass production with high-value pigment accumulation in *A. platensis*.

Figure 2. Effects of NaCl concentrations (0–300 mM) applied at day 0 (single-stage cultivation) or day 5 (two-stage cultivation) on fresh biomass (A, B) and phycocyanin yield (C, D) of *A. platensis*.

Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; and ***: $p < 0.001$.

Effects of different NaCl concentrations and IAA

The combined effects of NaCl and IAA (1 mg/L) on *A. platensis* growth and pigment biosynthesis varied with both NaCl concentrations and application time. In single-stage cultivation, the highest biomass yield after 10 days was obtained with 100 mM of NaCl + IAA (7.25 ± 0.27 g/L), representing 17% and 57% increases compared with 200 mM NaCl + IAA (6.19 ± 0.54 g/L) and 300 mM NaCl + IAA (4.62 ± 0.33 g/L), respectively (Figure 3). The phycocyanin content reached 13.07 ± 0.85 mg/g, which was 2.1-fold higher than with NaCl alone (6.39 ± 1.03 mg/g) and 1.3-fold higher than the control (10.35 ± 0.64 mg/g). Similar improvements have previously been reported by Silveira *et al.* (2024), highlighting the combined role of moderate salinity and IAA in enhancing phycocyanin productivity while maintaining biomass yield of *A. platensis*.

In two-stage cultivation, biomass production and phycocyanin accumulation were also improved (Figure 3). Specifically, the 100 mM of NaCl + 1 mg/L IAA treatment resulted in the highest fresh biomass (6.00 ± 0.14 g/L), which was approximately 1.3-fold higher than the unsupplemented control (4.47 ± 0.15 g/L). More importantly, phycocyanin content in the 100 mM of NaCl + 1 mg/L IAA treatment reached 12.05 ± 0.43 mg/g, nearly double that of the control (6.81 ± 0.39 mg/g, $p < 0.01$). These findings indicated that adding NaCl and IAA after an acclimation phase mitigated the inhibitory effects of salt stress on growth while stimulating pigment biosynthesis, likely due to enhanced osmotic adjustment, alleviation of oxidative stress, and upregulation of secondary metabolic pathways (Sun *et al.*, 2018). Delaying NaCl + IAA supplementation would allow *A. platensis* to establish robust biomass before reallocating metabolic resources toward phycobiliprotein biosynthesis. Two-stage cultivation strategies have previously been shown to enhance pigment productivity in cyanobacteria and microalgae by temporally separating growth and stress phases, thereby improving both biomass and metabolite yields (Yu *et al.*, 2023, Silveira *et al.*, 2024). In the current study, supplementation of NaCl + IAA after 5 days of cultivation likely alleviated osmotic stress during the initial growth phase, while subsequently activating signaling pathways for phycobiliprotein biosynthesis in *A. platensis* once maximum biomass accumulation has been achieved.

Figure 3. Effects of NaCl concentrations (0–300 mM) and IAA (1 mg/L) applied at day 0 (single-stage cultivation) or day 5 (two-stage cultivation) on fresh biomass (A, B) and phycocyanin yield (C, D) of *A. platensis*.

Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; and ***: $p < 0.001$.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that salt stress induced by NaCl, in combination with a two-stage cultivation strategy and the application of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA, 1 mg/L), significantly influenced the growth and phycocyanin biosynthesis in *A. platensis*. We observed that 100 mM NaCl applied at the start of growth produced the highest biomass (8.97 ± 2.80 g/L) but yielded relatively low phycocyanin content (6.39 ± 1.03 mg/g). Supplementation with IAA increased pigment production, raising the phycocyanin content up to 13.07 ± 0.85 mg/g. On the other hand, the two-stage cultivation approach, in which NaCl and IAA were supplemented after the initial biomass accumulation phase, also proved effective in increasing phycocyanin content (12.05 ± 0.43 mg/g) while maintaining sufficient biomass production. These findings indicated that optimizing both the timing of stress and phytohormone supplementation could alleviate growth inhibition and enhance pigment biosynthesis in *A. platensis*.

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TÁC ĐỘNG CỦA ĐỘ MẶN VÀ INDOLE-3-ACETIC ACID ĐẾN SINH TRƯỞNG VÀ SINH TỔNG HỢP PHYCOCYANIN Ở *Arthrospira platensis*

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TÓM TẮT

Arthrospira platensis là nguồn giàu khoáng chất, axit amin thiết yếu, và các sắc tố chống oxy hóa như chlorophyll và phycocyanin. Phycocyanin là sắc tố chống oxy hóa có giá trị cao; tuy nhiên, các phương pháp nuôi cấy nhằm gia tăng hàm lượng sắc tố này mà không ảnh hưởng đến sinh khối vẫn còn hạn chế. Nghiên cứu này đánh giá tác động hiệp đồng của stress mặn (NaCl, 100 - 300 mM) và indole-3-acetic acid (IAA, 1 mg/L) ngoại sinh đến quá trình sinh trưởng và sinh tổng hợp phycocyanin ở *A. platensis*. Kết quả sàng lọc ban đầu cho thấy 100 mM NaCl tạo ra sinh khối tảo cao nhất ($8,97 \pm 2,80$ g/L) nhưng lại làm giảm hàm lượng phycocyanin ($6,39 \pm 1,03$ mg/g). Để cải thiện năng suất sắc tố này, hai phương pháp nuôi cấy đã được khảo sát: bổ sung đồng thời IAA vào ngày 0 (nuôi cấy một giai đoạn) và vào ngày 5 (nuôi cấy hai giai đoạn). So với đối chứng, việc bổ sung đồng thời từ ngày 0 cho sinh khối tảo và hàm lượng phycocyanin cao nhất (lần lượt là $7,25 \pm 0,27$ g/L và $13,07 \pm 0,85$ mg/g), trong khi phương pháp nuôi cấy hai giai đoạn vẫn duy trì sinh khối ổn định ($6,00 \pm 0,14$ g/L) và gia tăng tích lũy phycocyanin ($12,05 \pm 0,43$ mg/g). Các kết quả này chứng minh rằng kết hợp độ mặn vừa phải với IAA giúp nâng cao năng suất phycocyanin và đồng thời duy trì sự sinh trưởng của tảo *A. platensis*, qua đó đưa ra được một chiến lược khả thi cho định hướng nuôi cấy tảo *A. platensis* giàu sắc tố.

Từ khóa: *Arthrospira platensis*, indole-3-acetic acid, phycocyanin, stress mặn, nuôi cấy hai giai đoạn.
